

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“NO MARRIED, NO CHILDREN”

No married, no children still I stand,
Whole and strong with open hands.
No vows to bind, no ties to keep,
Yet still I dream, I laugh, I hop.

They wonder why I walk alone,
No ring, no cries to call my own.
But peace has built its home in me,
And freedom sings in harmony.

I've loved in ways you cannot see,
In silent nights, in a verse.
In friends I hold like sacred light,
In silent mornings, soft and bright.

I am not less, I am not lost,
My path was mine, no matter cost.
No married, no children, still I'm free,
Complete in who I choose to be.